

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF WORK LIFE BALANCE OF IT EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT

It is known fact that India is a country with abundance of Human Resource or Human Capital in both skilled and unskilled categories. And we are able to get that there is a change in the roles of both men and woman since woman begun to enter the fields which weren't earlier toughed by them and one such sector is IT sector. Personal and professional life are two sides of the same coin and balance between the two is essential to have a healthy work life balance. With the increasing development and flexibility companies will are forced to implement certain things which are directly or indirectly demanded by the employees and work life balance is one such thing. And the objective of this article is to study about the impact of work life balance of woman belonging to IT sector. Through this study an in depth analysis about work life balance of woman belonging to IT sector can be received and various perceptions and expectations of the employees related to work life balance are highlighted in here.

KEYWORDS – Work life balance, Stress, Satisfaction, Wellbeing, and Overtime.

INTRODUCTION

The term work life balance is the act of balancing personal life and work life in such a way that one does not muddle with other and it is been one of the most focused topics that is essential in an organization in order to attract talented candidates and retain the existing talented candidates. The concept of Work Life Balance arose in the early 80s with the increase in the number of working woman professionals having children who are dependent on them. Employees both including male and female are living a complex and difficult life since the responsibilities in family and personal life increases. So work life balance became an essential thing for the employee to work in an organization and the management appreciated its importance. Hence maintaining work life balance is an important thing for any organization because that helps in reducing stress and help the employees from bursting out.

Making the employees enjoy the work life balance is not an easy task for all companies. Because companies would need additional staffs or employees to perform certain additional task at work sometime which can be adopted by large scale companies since they can afford paying for the additional salary which is not the same with small scale or medium scale enterprises. However companies can try their maximum to give a work life through which the employees can enjoy the work life balance. And this shall be done by the Human Resource

manager or Human Resource department by framing effective strategies and policies to give them enough space and time for their personal life which could be contribute to the company in form their works in return which in turn make the company into a successful one.

Lack of Work Life Balance would cause 'n' of problems such as physical problem, psychological disease like heart problems, exhaustion, weakening the immune system, stiff muscles, etc. If he hadn't had enough personal time he cannot look after himself and may encounter the above problems. If they didn't have had the problems mentioned because he had the work life balance thing he might feel committed to the job and develop satisfaction with the job which can make him deliver a good service at his work place, and he'll even plan on retaining in the job. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

Work Life Balance is a good thing that has to be followed in an organization for its holistic growth but it may become a disadvantage when too much flexibility is given in this area. For example the concept of work from home got very popular during the pandemic and many companies was inspired by this concept and was interested in work from home concept. However as a days rolled by during that time people begun to misuse the flexibility that is been given to them by faking the poor network connection, increasing the duration of breaks, etc.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Neeti Sharma (11, 2016) this study comes with the conclusion of comparison of Personal life with the work life. This highly sets the priorities of every individual as how they Priorities work from their family. In this study the samples are collected from 100 employees Including both male and female. They have used chi-square and t-test and found the stress level of the employees from which they came to conclusion that the stress is higher in female Compared with male as they manage both house hold work as well as office work. They carry the full burden and they couldn't maintain the work life balance. This considered as a big Problem and they came up with various programs to solve this. Then they enhanced the Better work culture.

Anja & Laura (June 20, 2011) this study has taken survey from 7867 workers from service sector in eight European countries. It was highly concentrated on the balance between the work and the private life. The main problem identified in this case was balancing the work with the work life balance among family. The proper work life balance is maintained the amount of stress will be at minimal level and productivity will be increased among the employees and the involvement and will be high in them. As findings it is been Stated that the emotional attachment with the family members have a good results whereas the person who is not so.

Preeti & Neha (August 2016) In this study it is been observed that the importance of work life balance Is highly important in everyone's life which enables all the employees and to balance their quality work and family responsibilities and it is found that currently there are wide programs conducted to main this in correct way, these programs helps in handling stress,

to rebalance life, and to avoid the conflicts. It is also stated that the work life balance is achieved through the work environment, culture, job satisfaction. The main thing is to be noted that the organisation will provide the requirement of one self and adaptable work culture with good support. This study was done with 194 samples with 200 questionnaire and SPSS software is been used

K V L Manasa & M Showry (August 2016) this study States the relationship between employees and the employers and the way how they maintain the work life balance. The workers must properly prioritize their work and family to maintain a proper work life balance in their work culture at the results they can avoid conflicts this study have stated lots of programs, job satisfaction, policies in order to regulate the work life balance in their life and these programs were the major influence in handling stress and to rebalance life. In the work place they were also offering less working time, paid leave, time for personal space, child care policy and casual Friday were also introduced. This reduced the stress. The finding of this study is the work life balance is highly influenced by organization practice.

Y.P.S Kanwar et.al the work for has the high impact on the employee turnover. In IT sector they mainly focuses on demotivation, Meaninglessness, exhaustion, and this study has found that the male respondents are highly satisfied with their job compared with female and female have higher role to perform they were handling both office work as well as household works. There are also some sensitive issues which affects the work life balance of the employees like gender equality, partiality among the workers in the work culture, the higher the burnout faced by employees the less will be the job satisfaction. The total sample size included in this is 313.

Nidhi Tewathia's study clearly states that when there is no proper work life balance it leads to overloaded stress. It is been noted that most of the time the stress arises from the work place and this stress generally increases the expectations of the employee and reduced the job satisfaction. Even with the more work life balance programs and services rendered like child care centre and this project. In work place the performance is based on how they manage their work life balance.

Shrabantee & Ayesa. The main concept of these review is to find the best part of someone's work life balance and to identify whether if they are interested in work family and the work place should be coordinated together and main. Work life balance is the main role played from the place of an HR manager. Where in this study 203 samples have been collected and the calculated in this is used for chicken and they have used. Thus, it results in more job satisfaction among the employees and the employee and turnover will be reduced

Sagar Gaikwad et.al This current research says that the women who are working are the one who tends to face such problem in higher rate as they need to balance both their work and family they need to be stronger enough both mentally and Physically. When the work environment is good the mental health of any person will be stable and will be able to face the work life balance. The questionnaire were distributed among 128 working women employees in IT sector, it was observed that the companies are trying to maintain the work life balance but in reality the employees still face problems in job performance.

Khaled and bataineh study's the main purpose the work life balance among the employees. It highly influence the work productivity as the happy employee will always come up with great work. It is important to maintain both physical and mental health this work life balance reduces the conflict arises in the work spaces and in personal life. The benefit is to improve the life quality of the employees and the effectiveness of the organization will be better the employee engagement of the workers will be with dedication vigour and absorption. In this study it is also observed that job satisfaction is positive in the work place is possible only if there is work life balance. The less work life balance results in low productivity to the result if there is no proper work life balance among that results in absenteeism, less performance there should be proper HRM (human resource management) practice to maintain the quality of the work and this reduces the employee turnover. Where in this the dependent variable is employee performance which is been mention in this study.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Primary objective – To study on the impact of work life balance of IT sector employees

Secondary objective - To study the impact of stress due to overstaying and work allocation on work life balance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative survey method for collecting the data from a pool of respondents by asking multiple survey questions. The questionnaire was prepared for finding the impact of work life balance among woman in IT sector. Time spent at work place, weekend holidays, depression were considered as factors that influence work life balance of the employees in office. The data's were collected through questionnaire was based on stratified sampling method. The questionnaire was framed on scalar basis (Likert's points scale). Data collected through online survey was primary in nature and it was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) statistical software and suggestions and conclusions were drawn to improve the objective of the research paper on work life balance.

The article has been done in one of metropolitan city Chennai and this was chosen to study about work life balance of employees. In this study quantitative approach is adopted as well as the statistical methods used to determine to determine the quality data for coherent output in the form of facts and data. The software used to analyze and to gather data to assess the quality insights and findings is referred as SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science).

HYPOTHESIS OF THE RESEARCH TEST

Null Hypothesis (HO) – There is no significant difference between overstaying in the office to finish the work and feeling tired or depressed because of work.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1) - There is significant difference between overstaying in the office to finish the work and feeling tired or depressed because of work.

Table 1: Statistics and Frequency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	26	68.4	68.4	68.4
	Female	12	31.6	31.6	100
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Age of the Respondents

Valid		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percentage
	18-20	16	42.1	42.1	42.1
	21-30	16	42.1	42.1	84.2
	31-40	2	5.3	5.3	89.5
	40above	4	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	100.0

INTERPRETATION

From Table no 1 it is been understood that out of the total respondents of 38, 26 of them were male and 12 of them were female. From Table no 2 we were able to see majority of the respondents belonged to the category between 18-20(42.1%) and 21-30(42.1%).

Table 3: Group Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
The amount of stress in my job is manageable	Male	26	3.8846	1.07059	0.20996
	Female	12	2.8333	1.64225	0.47408
Do you feel like you are able to balance your work life	Male	26	4.1538	0.83390	0.16354
	Female	12	3.3333	1.07309	0.30977

Table 4: Independent Sample T-Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig	t	Df
The amount of stress in my job is manageable	Equal variance assumed	4.504	0.041	2.367	36
	Equal variance not assumed			2.028	15.476
Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life	Equal variance assumed	0.485	0.491	2.573	36
	Equal variance not assumed			2.342	17.392

From the above table 4, that both the significance shows 0.05 hence there is significant difference between stress in work and the work life balance.

Table 5: One Way Anova

		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life	Btw groups	0.079	3	0.026	0.025	0.994
	Within Groups	35.500	34	1.044		
	Total	37	37			
The amount of stress in my job is manageable	Btw groups	8.020	3	2.673	1.531	0.224
	Within groups	59.375	34	1.7436		
	Total	67.395	37			

Table no 5 shows the significant values. In this case majority of the variables shows that greater than 0.05. Hence there is no significant difference between stress in the job and work life balance.

Table 6: Corelation

		I over stay in the office to finish the work	I feel tired or depressed because of work
I overstay in the office to finish the work	Pearson Correlation	1	0.469
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.003
	N		38
I feel tired or depressed because of work	Pearson Correlation	0.469	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	
	N	38	38

Above Table no 6 shows the significance is 0.469 which is a moderate positive correlation between a person overstaying to finish the work and getting tired because of work.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research is focused on the work life balance which has the major part in performance input of the employees be it woman or men and therefore how it affects the overall organizational output as well as the individual, organizational goals and other aspects. It was observed in the survey that majority of the respondents felt that having a work life balance is one of the foremost issues that can be incurred through various problems. Hence such problems or issues can be solved by understanding the needs of the employees and allowing some kind of flexibility which would make them not to lose the interest in their current job and make them feel motivated by creating a positive work environment which would increase the individual productivity which will then contribute to the organizational productivity. Thus the organization or the HR manager whose job is to look after the employees and their welfare will have to develop an interpersonal relationship which would make them convey their problems without any hesitation so that there would be no stress issues, in every formal organization should be an informal organization is an apt suggestion for understanding the needs and wants of the employees which would create a stress free environment.

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